

1 Supplementary Information

2

3 **Figure S1:** Map of terrestrial ecosystems, 2020. Source: Authors' elaboration.

4

5 **Figure S2:** Map of terrestrial ecosystems, 2050 SC1. Source: Source: Authors'
 6 elaboration.

7

8 **Figure S3:** Map of terrestrial ecosystems, 2050 SC2. Source: Authors' elaboration.

9

10 **Figure S4:** Land condition for 2010 (a), 2020 (b), 2050 SC1 (c), and 2050 SC2 (d).

11 Source: Authors' elaboration.

12

13 **Figure S5:** Condition index for the year 2020 by MVCA for: (a) forest ecosystems, (b)
 14 agricultural ecosystems, (c) urban & industrial ecosystems and (d) land. Dark shading
 15 represents high condition except for urban ecosystems, where darker red shows lower
 16 condition. Source: Authors' elaboration.

17

18 **Figure S6:** Land index change for (a) 2010-2020, and modelled change for (b) 2020-2050
 19 SC1, and (c) 2020-2050 SC2. Darker shading represents degradation (negative values).
 20 Source: Authors' elaboration.

21 Presenting results by MVCA is useful in that interventions may be planned and
 22 resources allocated with respect to risks, opportunities, and individual capabilities at
 23 this administrative level. This follows the Principle of Subsidiarity in governance, which
 24 prescribes that decision-making should be devolved to the lowest level that is closest to
 25 where impacts are felt. Since impacts are localised, then decisions are best made at
 26 the MVCAs with local government playing a critical role in land use planning. For
 27 instance, Nature-based Solutions to reduce climate vulnerabilities (while enhancing
 28 natural capital) always take place at the MVCA level. Figure S5 displays condition index
 29 values in 2020 as baseline, whereas Figure S6 shows index change from 2010 to 2020,
 30 and anticipated changes from 2020 to 2050 (SC1 and SC2).